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Trust in the Police Forces in the Italian Regions

It grew on average by 2.4% between 2012 and 2022 in the Italian regions

Istat calculates trust in the police. The variable is calculated as the average score of trust in the police and firefighters (on a scale from 0 to 10) expressed by people aged 14 and over. The data refers to the Italian regions in the period 2012-2022.

Ranking of the Italian regions by value of trust in law enforcement in 2022. Trentino Alto Adige, Emilia Romagna and Umbria are in first place for value of trust in law enforcement in 2022 with a value of 7,7 units. In the middle of the table are Piedmont, Lombardy and Lazio with a value of 7.5 units. Puglia and Calabria close the ranking with a value of 7.2 units and Campania with a value of 7 units.

Ranking of the Italian regions by percentage change in trust in the police force between 2012 and 2022. Calabria is in first place for the value of the percentage change in trust in the police force with a value equal to 5.88% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 6.8 units up to a value of 7.2 units. Lazio follows with a value equal to 5.63% corresponding to a variation from an amount of 7.1 units up to a value of 7.5 units. In third place Umbria with a variation equal to an amount of 5.48% equal to a variation from 7.3 units up to 7.7 units. In the middle of the table is Sicily with +2.74% corresponding to a variation from 7.3 units up to 7.5 units or equal to +0.2 units. Followed by Liguria and Veneto, each of which recorded a value of 2.7% corresponding to a variation from 7.4 units up to a value of 7.6 units or equal to 0.2 units. Friuli Venezia Giulia and Marche close the ranking with a variation of 0.00%, followed by Abruzzo with a value of -1.33%. On average, trust in the police grew by 2.4% in the Italian regions between 2012 and 2022.

Trust in law enforcement in the Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2022. Trust in law enforcement grew in all Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2022. Trust in law enforcement increased grew above all in Central Italy with a value of +4.17%, in the South with a value of +2.86%, in the South with +2.82%, in the Islands with +2.74%, in the North East with +2.7%, in the North and North-West with +1.35%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Silhouette coefficient. The data highlights the presence of two clusters:

- Cluster 1: Basilicata, Campania, Calabria, Molise, Puglia, Sicily.
- Cluster 2: Piedmont, Veneto, Tuscany, Emilia Romagna, Friuli Venezia Giulia, Trentino Alto Adige, Liguria, Lombardy, Valle d'Aosta, Abruzzo, Sardinia, Umbria, Lazio, Marche.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters, it is possible to note that the average value of cluster 2-C2 is higher than the average value of cluster 1-C1. It follows that $C2 > C1$. The regions making up C2 are essentially regions of Central-Northern Italy, with the only exceptions of Sardinia

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and Abruzzo. The C1 regions, however, are essentially southern regions. Therefore we can generally note a level of trust in the police force which appears to be lower in the southern regions than in the northern ones, with the exception of Sardinia and Abruzzo. However, since Cluster 2 is made up of approximately 14 regions, equal to approximately 70% of the available data, we believe it is necessary to move to a level of $k > 2$ although sub-optimal in the sense of the Silhouette coefficient. In fact, the optimal level of clustering is $k = 2$. However, due to the overabundance of regions within cluster 2, we set a level of $k = 3$, even knowing that this value of k is suboptimal in the sense of the Silhouette coefficient. Therefore we can see that by setting $k = 3$ we have:

- Cluster 1: Basilicata, Campania, Calabria, Molise;
- Cluster 2: Friuli Venezia Giulia, Liguria, Trentino Alto Adige, Veneto, Piedmont, Emilia Romagna, Tuscany, Lombardy, Abruzzo, Umbria, Valle d'Aosta;
- Cluster 3: Sicily, Lazio, Puglia, Marche, Sardinia.

From the point of view of the ordering of the clusters, the following structure results: $C2 > C3 > C1$. That is, the regions that have the greatest degree of trust towards the police are the regions of Central-Northern Italy. The second cluster for average value of trust towards the police is represented by cluster 3 made up of regions with a mix of regions from the Center and the South. Finally, Cluster 1 made up of the remaining regions of Southern Italy. The only region in Southern Italy to have high levels in terms of trust in the police force is Abruzzo which in fact participates in Cluster 2. We can note that in the transition from the clustering with $k = 2$ to the clustering with $k = 3$ it appears the distance between the regions of the Centre-North and the regions of the Centre-South is more evident. However, there remains a significant aggregate of regions that are absolutely convergent in demonstrating high levels of trust towards the police, which in the case of $k = 3$ is given by Cluster 2. Finally, the case of Abruzzo is very particular. In fact, Abruzzo is the only region in Southern Italy to remain in the dominant cluster despite increasing the value of k from $k = 2$ to $k = 3$.

Conclusions. From the analysis conducted it is possible to identify the following propositions:

- The value of trust in law enforcement increased in all Italian regions between 2012 and 2022;
- The value of trust in law enforcement increased in the Italian macro-regions between 2012 and 2022;
- The Central-North regions tend to have a higher level of trust in the police than the corresponding value in the Central-South regions;
- Abruzzo is the only southern region to have a level of trust in the police in line with the northern regions.

In summary, we can note that trust towards the police tends to be much higher than trust towards parties, trust towards the judicial system, trust towards parliament and generalized trust or trust in compared to others. The police therefore have a very important role in creating a sense of trust among the population towards the institutions. Based on Istat data, it is possible to state that the police are the only state institution that is highly appreciated by the population. Therefore, the credibility of the State is closely linked to the efficiency and operation of law enforcement at a regional level.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

Funding. The author received no financial support for the research, authorship, and/or publication of this article.

Declaration of Competing Interest. The author declares that there is no conflict of interests regarding the publication of this manuscript. In addition, the ethical issues, including plagiarism, informed consent, misconduct, data fabrication and/or falsification, double publication.

Acknowledgements. I am grateful to the teaching staff of the LUM University “Giuseppe Degennaro” and to the management of the LUM Enterprise s.r.l. for the constant inspiration to continue our scientific research work undeterred.

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Appendix

Regione	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Piemonte	7,4	7,3	7,2	7,1	7,3	7,4	7,3	7,6	7,7	7,6	7,5
Valle d'Aosta	7,3	7,2	7,2	7,2	7,4	7,3	7,3	7,3	7,5	7,5	7,3
Liguria	7,4	7,4	7,5	7,2	7,3	7,5	7,6	7,6	7,9	7,6	7,6
Lombardia	7,4	7,3	7,1	7	7,3	7,4	7,3	7,4	7,7	7,4	7,5
Trentino-Alto Adige/	7,5	7,5	7,4	7,4	7,6	7,6	7,5	7,6	7,7	7,6	7,7
Veneto	7,4	7,3	7,1	7,1	7,2	7,5	7,4	7,5	7,7	7,6	7,6
Friuli-Venezia Giulia	7,6	7,4	7,3	7,4	7,5	7,6	7,5	7,6	7,7	7,6	7,6
Emilia-Romagna	7,4	7,5	7,3	7,2	7,4	7,3	7,4	7,6	7,7	7,7	7,7
Toscana	7,3	7,3	7,2	7,1	7,2	7,5	7,4	7,5	7,7	7,5	7,4
Umbria	7,3	7	7	7,1	7,1	7,3	7,3	7,7	7,6	7,8	7,7
Marche	7,4	7,4	7	7,1	7,2	7,1	7,3	7,6	7,3	7,3	7,4
Lazio	7,1	7,2	7	7	7,3	7,3	7,3	7,5	7,4	7,4	7,5
Abruzzo	7,5	7,2	7	6,9	7,1	7,5	7,3	7,5	7,7	7,5	7,4
Molise	7,1	7,2	6,9	6,6	6,9	7	6,8	7,3	7,4	7,2	7,3
Campania	6,9	6,7	6,7	6,4	7	6,8	6,8	7	7	7,2	7
Puglia	7	7	7	7	7,2	7	7,2	7,5	7,4	7,2	7,2
Basilicata	7	6,8	6,6	6,7	6,9	7	6,9	7,3	7,3	7,1	7,3
Calabria	6,8	6,7	6,6	6,8	7	7,1	7	7,4	7,5	7,4	7,2
Sicilia	7,3	7,3	6,9	6,8	7,1	6,9	7,3	7,6	7,4	7,3	7,5
Sardegna	7,2	7,2	7,1	7,1	7,3	7,4	7,2	7,4	7,3	7,5	7,4

Macro-Regioni	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Nord	7,4	7,3	7,2	7,1	7,3	7,4	7,4	7,5	7,7	7,6	7,5
Nord-ovest	7,4	7,3	7,2	7,1	7,3	7,4	7,4	7,5	7,7	7,5	7,5
Nord-est	7,4	7,4	7,2	7,2	7,3	7,5	7,4	7,5	7,7	7,6	7,6
Centro	7,2	7,2	7,1	7	7,2	7,4	7,3	7,5	7,5	7,5	7,5
Mezzogiorno	7,1	7	6,9	6,8	7,1	7	7,1	7,4	7,3	7,3	7,3
Sud	7	6,8	6,8	6,7	7,1	6,9	7	7,3	7,3	7,3	7,2
Isole	7,3	7,3	7	6,9	7,2	7,1	7,3	7,5	7,3	7,4	7,5
Italia	7,3	7,2	7	7	7,2	7,3	7,3	7,5	7,5	7,5	7,4

